

A Hospital-Based Study to Evaluate Relationship between Serum 25 (OH) Vitamin D and Insulin Resistance in PrediabetesVijay Gadhia¹, Darshankumar Parmar², Sanket G. Makwana³¹Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Jeevandeep Hospital, Morbi, Gujarat, India²Consultant, Department of General Medicine, Aayush Multi-speciality Hospital, Morbi, Gujarat, India³Associate Professor, Department of General Medicine, C U Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to evaluate relationship between serum 25 (OH) vitamin D and insulin resistance in prediabetes.**Methods:** The present study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine and the sample selected was 60 diabetics, 50 pre-diabetes and 40 healthy control individuals. Inclusion criteria used was subjects in age ranged 40-75 years of either gender with persistent IFG or IGT over 2 OGTTs.**Results:** Maximum pre-diabetes subjects (16) had serum 25 (OH) D >30 ng/ml, diabetes (20) between 21-30 ng/ml and control (15) >30 ng/ml. In diabetes, pre-diabetes and control subjects had BMI of 24.6 kg/m², 25.5 kg/m² and 23.7 kg/m², waist circumference of 91.7 cm, 88.2 cm and 86.4 cm, waist- height ratio of 0.84, 0.52 and 0.50, waist- hip ratio of 0.94, 0.90 and 0.86, LDL- C of 97.3 mg/dl, 106.4 mg/dl and 98.6 mg/dl, HDL- C of 46.2 mg/dl, 48.4 mg/dl and 49.6 mg/dl, TG of 148.4 mg/dl, 146.4 mg/dl and 117.4 mg/dl respectively. HbA1C found to be 7.3%, 6.5% and 5.6%, HOMA2-IR was 2.52, 1.52 and 0.82, HOMA2-β was 63.7, 82.6 and 86.4 and 25 (OH) D level was 25.5 ng/ml, 24.2 ng/ml and 22.8 ng/ml. A significant difference was observed (P< 0.05). 1 hour PG blood glucose had statistically significant positive correlation with FBS and 2 hours PG blood glucose (P< 0.05).**Conclusion:** It is important to understand association of vitamin D and diabetes. Vitamin-D deficiency led to worsening of insulin resistance in individuals with prediabetes.**Keywords:** Prediabetes, Insulin Resistance, Hypovitaminosis-D, Hyperglycemia, Serum Vitamin D.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Insulin resistance (IR) is a state of metabolic disorder in which the responsiveness of insulin-dependent tissues is reduced, leading to an elevated risk of diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular diseases (CVD). The insulin hormone helps in controlling the amount of glucose in the blood. When there is Insulin Resistance in the body, the target tissues start ignoring Insulin's signal that is to get the glucose out of the bloodstream and put it into our cells. Resultantly, the entry of glucose into the cells becomes difficult, and it starts accumulating in the blood, which ultimately leads to chronic hyperinsulinemia. [1]

Hyperinsulinemia glycemic clamp is the gold standard test for the assessment of IR; nevertheless, because of high associated cost, it is not commonly used. HOMA-IR (Homeostatic Model Assessment of Insulin Resistance) is the most widely used indicator for IR assessment, and it is calculated

using plasma glucose and serum insulin levels. However, HOMA-IR is not viable for large-scale studies due to the relatively high cost of serum insulin estimation. Recently, numerous studies have suggested the Triglycerides and Glucose (TyG) index as an efficient marker for the assessment of IR. [2-5] The TyG index is a low-cost marker and easier to calculate as its calculation only requires serum triglycerides (TG) and fasting blood glucose levels. Vitamin D deficiency is a serious public health concern all over the world. It is estimated that approximately more than one billion people worldwide had insufficient levels of vitamin D in 2007. [6]

A decreased amount of serum 25(OH)D, calcitriol [1,25(OH)2D] and raised parathyroid hormone (PTH) can increase intracellular calcium in adipocytes, which can stimulate lipogenesis predisposing a patient to further weight gain and thus increasing the risk of diabetes. [7] Vitamin D

deficiency is prevalent in India. Various studies from northern and southern parts of India proved the deficiency of vitamin D in our population. [8-10] Data regarding association of 25(OH) D with insulin resistance in Indians is very limited. Pittas et al. summarized the role of vitamin D on glucose metabolism. [11,12] Many Cross sectional and case control studies suggest an inverse association between vitamin D status, glucose intolerance and type 2 diabetes. [13,14] This could be due the distribution of Vitamin D receptors (VDR) on pancreatic beta cells, adipose tissue and skeletal muscle. Vitamin D status influences insulin secretion or insulin sensitivity. The effect of vitamin D on insulin secretion may be mediated by changes in intracellular calcium concentration in beta cells. [15,16]

The aim of the present study was to evaluate relationship between serum 25 (OH) vitamin D and insulin resistance in prediabetes.

Materials and Methods

The present study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, Jeevandeep Hospital, Morbi, Gujarat, India for 1 year and the sample selected was 60 diabetics, 50 pre-diabetes and 40 healthy control individuals. Inclusion criteria used was

subjects in age ranged 40-75 years of either gender with persistent IFG or IGT over 2 OGTTs.

A case history file containing information regarding gender, waist circumference (WC), hip circumference (HC), waist- hip ratio, HbA1C and lipid profile such as LDL- C, HDL- C and triglyceride was made. Based on the vitamin-D status, individual with vitamin-D sufficiency [25(OH)D \geq 30 ng/ml] were prediabetes, vitamin-D insufficiency [25(OH)D: 20-30 ng/ml] were diabetes, mild vitamin-D deficiency [25(OH)D: 10-20 ng/ml] and severe vitamin-D deficiency [25(OH)D <10 ng/ml] were controls. Serum insulin was estimated using solid phase, enzyme labelled chemiluminescent immunometric assay. Insulin resistance in basal state was calculated using HOMA2-IR (homeostatic model assessment-insulin resistance) and beta cell function was estimated using HOMA2- β . 1 hour post glucose (1hPG) blood glucose >155 mg/dl was strong predictor for future risk of T2D. Results of the present study after recording all relevant data were subjected for statistical inferences using chi- square test. The level of significance was significant if p value was below 0.05.

Results

Table 1: Level of vitamin D in individuals

Category	Serum 25 (OH) D			
	<10	11-20	21-30	>30
Pre-diabetes (50)	9	11	14	16
Diabetes (60)	12	15	20	13
Control (40)	5	8	12	15

Maximum pre- diabetes subjects (16) had serum 25 (OH) D >30 ng/ml, diabetes (20) between 21-30 ng/ml and control (15) >30 ng/ml.

Table 2: Relationship between anthropometric parameters and diabetes status

Parameters	Diabetes	Pre-diabetes	Normal	P value
BMI	24.6	25.4	23.7	>0.05
Waist circumference	91.7	88.2	86.4	<0.05
Waist- height ratio	0.84	0.52	0.50	<0.05
Waist- hip ratio	0.94	0.90	0.86	<0.05
LDL- C	97.3	106.4	98.6	<0.05
HDL- C	46.2	48.4	49.6	<0.05
TG	148.4	146.4	117.4	<0.05
HbA1C	7.3	6.5	5.6	<0.05
HOMA2-IR	2.52	1.52	0.82	<0.05
HOMA2- β	63.7	82.6	86.4	>0.05
25 (OH) D	25.5	24.2	22.8	>0.05

In diabetes, pre-diabetes and control subjects had BMI of 24.6 kg/m², 25.5 kg/m² and 23.7 kg/m², waist circumference of 91.7 cm, 88.2 cm and 86.4 cm, waist- height ratio of 0.84, 0.52 and 0.50, waist- hip ratio of 0.94, 0.90 and 0.86, LDL- C of 97.3 mg/dl, 106.4 mg/dl and 98.6 mg/dl, HDL- C of 46.2 mg/dl, 48.4 mg/dl and 49.6 mg/dl, TG of

148.4 mg/dl, 146.4 mg/dl and 117.4 mg/dl respectively. HbA1C found to be 7.3%, 6.5% and 5.6%, HOMA2-IR was 2.52, 1.52 and 0.82, HOMA2- β was 63.7, 82.6 and 86.4 and 25 (OH) D level was 25.5 ng/ml, 24.2 ng/ml and 22.8 ng/ml. A significant difference was observed (P< 0.05).

Table 3: Correlation between vitamin-D status and insulin resistance, systemic inflammation and dyslipidaemia in prediabetes

Correlation variables		Variable adjusted	Pearson's correlation	P value
Parameter 1	Parameter 2			
25 (OH) D	HOMA2-IR	BMI, HbA1C	-0.32	<0.05
25 (OH) D	HOMA2-β	BMI, HbA1C	-0.16	>0.05
25 (OH) D	HbA1C	-	-0.07	>0.05
1 hour PG	FBS	-	0.38	<0.05
1 hour PG	2 hours PG	-	0.54	<0.05

1 hour PG blood glucose had statistically significant positive correlation with FBS and 2 hours PG blood glucose ($P < 0.05$).

Discussion

Subjects with impaired fasting glucose (IFG) and/or impaired glucose tolerance (IGT) are referred to as having prediabetes. [17] Indian diabetes prevention programme-1 (IDPP-1) reported the annual risk of progression to overt diabetes from IGT approximately 18% and 2.5% in the diabetes prevention trial (DPT) in the Chinese diabetes prevention study. Prediabetes is frequently associated with obesity and other components of metabolic syndrome. [18] Obesity in turn is commonly associated with hypovitaminosis-D due to the capacity of adipose tissue to store 25-hydroxy vitamin-D [25(OH)D] making it biologically unavailable. [19] A decreased amount of serum 25(OH)D, calcitriol [1,25(OH)₂D] and raised parathyroid hormone (PTH) can increase intracellular calcium in adipocytes, which can stimulate lipogenesis predisposing a patient to further weight gain and thus increasing the risk of diabetes. [20,21] Prediabetes is a stage earlier in the hyperglycemia/diabetes continuum where individuals are at increased risk of developing diabetes and where prevention efforts, including lifestyle modification or pharmacologic intervention, have been shown to be effective in preventing or delaying the onset of diabetes. [22]

Maximum pre-diabetes subjects (16) had serum 25 (OH) D >30 ng/ml, diabetes (20) between 21-30 ng/ml and control (15) >30 ng/ml. Several studies have shown that lower 25- hydroxyvitamin D (25[OH]D) levels are related to an increased risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). [23-25] In diabetes, pre-diabetes and control subjects had BMI of 24.6 kg/m², 25.5 kg/m² and 23.7 kg/m², waist circumference of 91.7 cm, 88.2 cm and 86.4 cm, waist- height ratio of 0.84, 0.52 and 0.50, waist- hip ratio of 0.94, 0.90 and 0.86, LDL- C of 97.3 mg/dl, 106.4 mg/dl and 98.6 mg/dl, HDL- C of 46.2 mg/dl, 48.4 mg/dl and 49.6 mg/dl, TG of 148.4 mg/dl, 146.4 mg/dl and 117.4 mg/dl respectively. HbA1C found to be 7.3%, 6.5% and 5.6%, HOMA2-IR was 2.52, 1.52 and 0.82, HOMA2-β was 63.7, 82.6 and 86.4 and 25 (OH) D level was 25.5 ng/ml, 24.2 ng/ml and 22.8 ng/ml. Dutta et al

[26] evaluated the relationship between vitamin-D status and insulin resistance on one hundred fifty-seven individuals with prediabetes. It was found in this study that vitamin-D deficiency/insufficiency was found in 115 (73.25%) individuals with prediabetes. Shankar et al [27] examined the 12,719 participants (52.5% women) who were free of diabetes. Serum 25(OH)D levels were categorized into quartiles (<17.7, 17.8–24.5, 24.6–32.4, >32.4 ng/mL). Prediabetes was defined as a 2-h glucose concentration of 140–199 mg/dL, or a fasting glucose concentration of 110–125 mg/dL, or an A1C value of 5.7–6.4%. Lower serum 25(OH)D levels were associated with prediabetes after adjusting for age, sex, race/ethnicity, season, geographic region, smoking, alcohol intake, BMI, outdoor physical activity, milk consumption, dietary vitamin D, blood pressure, serum cholesterol, C-reactive protein, and glomerular filtration rate.

A significant difference was observed ($P < 0.05$). 1 hour PG blood glucose had statistically significant positive correlation with FBS and 2 hours PG blood glucose ($P < 0.05$). Farouche et al [28] included a total of 524 nondiabetic men and women, aged 40–69 years and found that age-adjusted baseline mean serum 25(OH)D was greater in men (64.5 nmol/l) than women (57.2 nmol/l) and varied with season (highest late summer). Baseline 25(OH)D was associated inversely with 10-year risk of hyperglycemia, insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome z score after adjustment for age, sex, smoking, BMI, season, and baseline value of each metabolic outcome variable. Associations with 2-h glucose, insulin, and HOMA-IR remained significant after further adjustment for IGF-1, parathyroid hormone, calcium, physical activity, and social class.

Conclusion

It is important to understand association of vitamin D and diabetes. Vitamin-D deficiency led to worsening of insulin resistance in individuals with prediabetes. Vit D deficiency is common in prediabetic state and subjects having severe vitamin D deficiency (<10 ng/ml), had the worst insulin resistance. Our study results help in strongly proposing vitamin D levels as an early marker for

diabetes and help in recommending vitamin D to be prescribed in the pre diabetic stage itself.

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